

SOP Title	Taking staff hand swab samples for TRACS-Liverpool study		
Version	1	SOP reference	TRACS_SOP_002
Written By	Sally Forrest	Date	11/01/23
Reviewed By	Claudia McKeown	Date	19/08/24
Authorised By		Date	

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Introduction

The TRACS-Liverpool (Tracking AMR Across Care Settings in Liverpool) study aims to track transmission of extended-spectrum beta lactamase and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (ESBL-E/CPE) in hospitals and care homes in Liverpool. We will do this by recruiting care homes and hospital patients and collecting stool and associated environmental samples over a period of months. By testing these samples for ESBL-E/CPE organisms and using gene sequencing techniques to track bacteria we hope to identify where transmission of resistant bacteria is happening. We then aim to combine this information with routine data on antibiotic usage and patterns of care and will work with the hospital flow teams and participating care homes to co-design and pilot interventions to block transmission and, ultimately, reduce the number of drug-resistant infections.

1. Purpose

This method is applicable to the taking of staff hand swabs associated with the TRACS-Liverpool Study.

2. Responsibilities

- Collection team
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Recording barcodes and swab locations in RedCap software.
- Laboratory staff
 - Receive samples from collection team and complete sample collection log

3. Definitions and Abbreviations

TRACS	Tracking AMR Across Care Settings
LSTM	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
ESBL-E	Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase-producing Enterobacterales

4. Related Documents

TRACS_SOP_004	Environmental swab processing
TRACS_SOP_002	Staff hand sampling
Risk Assessment for Work with Hazardous Biological Agent_TRACS	Risk assessment

5. Risk Assessment

<i>Hazard (Cause and Consequence)</i>	<i>Affected Groups</i>	<i>Existing controls (e.g., PPE...)</i>
<i>Biological Hazards</i>		
Environmental swabs: potential infection	Collection team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear PPE (gloves) when handling swabs • For spills on site, refer to local guidance. • For spills on transport to the laboratory refer to section 7.3
<i>Chemical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A
<i>Physical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A

6. Sample Collection/Workflow

6.1 Study outline

Collect staff hand swabs from areas outlined in TRACS study protocol and deliver to LSTM lab for processing.

6.2 Recording swab data

Use RedCap software to record all data.

7. Procedure

7.1 Equipment and Reagents

7.1.1 Consumables required

Materials	Company/Code
Gloves	Starlabs/SG-C-(sizw: S, M, L)
FOAM SWAB® Standard Tip	MWE/ MW941
Yellow clinical waste bag	Appleton Woods/KC309
Clear storage bags	Fisher/BAJ-340-091N
Transport box	Sarstedt/95.1720
Timer	Fisher/ 13023023
15mL falcons with sterile PBS	Fisher/352096/10010023

7.2 Staff swab sample collection

1. Ensure participating staff have had the opportunity to read the participant information sheet explaining the procedure.
2. Record the sample data by completing the relevant information on the study form and linking the barcode label on the swab tube in RedCap.
3. Remove the swab from the tube and dip into a tube containing sterile PBS to moisten.
4. Carefully swab all areas of the healthcare worker's hand for 20 seconds.
5. Return the swab to the transport tube and place into a storage bag. Place the bag into the storage box. Multiple swabs can be placed into storage bags, ensure the bag is sealed when full.
6. Healthcare workers are advised to use hand sanitizer or wash their hands with soap and water following swabbing.
7. Discard the wipes and any other waste into the yellow clinical waste bags.
8. Continue until all staff have been swabbed. Change to a new tube of sterile PBS every 10 samples and mark on sample sheet when new aliquot of PBS has been used.

9. Discard wipes, used gloves and any other waste into the clinical waste bags or appropriate yellow bags on the ward.
10. Transport samples to the LSTM laboratory and store at 4°C until processing according to TRACS_SOP_004

7.3 Spill procedure

In the unlikely event of a spill occurring, follow local guidelines for how to clean up. If samples are spilt/opened during transport to the laboratory, cross contamination may have occurred. Any open swab tubes will be transferred to a class II microbiological safety cabinet and dealt with according to laboratory SOPs. The details will be recorded, and a decision made by a senior member of the lab team whether to process the samples or discard them.

8. Review History

19/08/23 - Reviewed and no changes needed.